

A new definition for the thesis: What is life?

Life is a dynamic system fluctuating between competition and cooperation through self-reference, and its relative functionality is shaped by the support and selective pressure from the environment.

This occurs through the interplay of self-organization and interaction with the environment, resulting in the adaptive organization of the ambivalence in space-time.

The outcome is the emergence of relatively functional dissipative structures, which then organize adaptive spatiotemporal paths, pumping out entropy.

These dissipative structures continue to evolve, forming structures of increasingly higher order.

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